

Advances in the Instrument Control System Software Design for MORFEO: Integration with MICADO and the post-focal Deformable Mirrors in the ELT Environment

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ABSTRACT

MORFEO is the multi-conjugate adaptive optics (MCAO) module for the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) of ESO. It is conceived to provide diffraction-limited imaging over a wide field of view, serving MICADO, the ELT's first-light near-infrared imager and spectrograph, and supporting a future second-generation instrument (HARMONI). The system is now progressing toward the Final Design Review with significant updates underway in the architecture of its Instrument Control System Software (ICSS). This paper presents the latest updates to the design of the MORFEO ICSS. Particular attention is paid to integration with the MICADO ICSS and to control and monitoring of the DMs. When operating in MCAO mode, the Deformable Mirrors (DMs) are controlled by the MORFEO Real-Time Computer. In contrast, in single-conjugate AO mode, the DM's shape is predefined and set by the MORFEO ICSS. MICADO and MORFEO are two independent instruments, but they each need to use functions of the other system to be properly configured and used. Two interface libraries are provided for this purpose. The first offers MICADO a way to use MORFEO functionalities at the observation block level, in a totally transparent way, hiding the AO complexities. The second provides access to specific MICADO functionalities needed for certain calibrations of the AO module. We discuss the adopted design solutions and ongoing efforts to ensure robustness, modularity, and seamless integration within the ELT control environment.

Keywords: MORFEO, Software, ELT, MICADO, Adaptive Optics

1. INTRODUCTION

The Multi-conjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations (MORFEO) is the post-focal adaptive optics module being developed for the Extremely Large Telescope^[4]. MORFEO is designed to operate in synergy with the MICADO^[2] near-infrared imaging camera and, in the future, with an additional instrument (HARMONY). Its primary objective is to provide advanced AO capabilities that maximize the scientific return of MICADO by delivering diffraction-limited performance under a wide range of atmospheric conditions.

MORFEO supports two distinct AO modes: multi-conjugate adaptive optics (MCAO) and single-conjugate adaptive optics (SCAO). In MCAO mode, atmospheric turbulence is corrected at multiple altitudes using the ELT deformable mirror (M4) in combination with two additional internal MORFEO deformable mirrors. This configuration enables compensation for turbulence distributed throughout the atmospheric volume, significantly improving the corrected field of view. High-order turbulence measurements in MCAO rely on six sodium laser guide stars, providing a three-dimensional reconstruction of atmospheric distortions. To complement the LGS,

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three Natural Guide Stars are used to correct for low-order aberrations such as tip-tilt, focus, and astigmatism. In SCAO mode, turbulence correction is performed exclusively by the M4 deformable mirror, with wavefront sensing carried out using a single NGS. Unlike MCAO, this mode does not employ LGS and is being developed in close collaboration with the MICADO consortium. SCAO offers a simpler configuration optimized for high-strehl ratio correction within a smaller corrected field of view.

The baseline design of MORFEO comprises five principal subsystems: (i) the Post Focal Relay Optics (PFRO), which houses the optical relay components and the main calibration unit; (ii) the LGS wave-front sensor module, containing six sensors dedicated to laser guide star measurements; (iii) the NGS wave-front sensor (NGS-WFS) module, divided into the low-order and reference WFS units; (iv) the thermal control system. This paper illustrates the latest advances in the implementation of instrument control software systems.

Section 1 gives an overview of the MORFEO control software architecture; Section 2 describes the software interface that allows communication between MORFEO and MICADO; Section 3 focuses on the interface and control of the Post Focal DMs; Section 4 provides a conclusion and prospects.

2. MORFEO ICSS ARCHITECTURE

2.1 General overview

The MORFEO Instrument Control Software System (ICSS) provides two Adaptive Optics (AO) operational modes to support the MICADO client instrument: Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) and Single-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO). This distinction is explicitly reflected in the software architecture. The ICSS is designed with a modular architecture that clearly separates the control of SCAO and MCAO functionalities, allowing them to operate independently. MORFEO ICSS also interfaces with two Real-Time Computers (one for SCAO and one for MCAO) and with the Central Control Software, which manages the ELT mirrors and the laser launch telescope. The Function Control System (FCS) and the Detector Control System (DCS) control the hardware subsystems:

- **The Function Control System** is a dedicated software application responsible for controlling actuators and sensors. Each FCS consists of a high-level software component running on the instrument workstation and a low-level software component running on the Local Control System. MORFEO foresees five FCS instances in MCAO mode (controlling the PFRO, THCS, Calibration Unit, LORWFS, and LGSWFS functions) and three FCS instances in SCAO mode.
- **The Detector Control System** controls and monitors the AO WFS cameras for both MCAO and SCAO modes, using the ESO Camera Control Framework (CCF) to operate and supervise the technical cameras.

The monitoring and coordination of the various subsystems is also organized in modular mode. Indeed, there is a **System Supervisor** that provides a global overview of the system status and monitors both the SCAO and MCAO subsystem supervisors. These two monitor: the status of the FCS instances, the auxiliary loops, the offload processes, both MCAO and SCAO RTCs, and the status of the MCAO Observation Coordination Manager (OCM) service. The OCM is the software component responsible for orchestrating instrument observations by managing exposure execution and coordinating the creation of Data Products. In general, the MORFEO AO module is not expected to produce scientific data, except when MICADO performs an exposure. In this case, the status and AO parameters required for FITS headers are recorded by the MORFEO ICSS. MORFEO therefore acquires metadata from its data producers (FCS, DCS, RTC, Auxiliary Loop processes, and CCF) each time the client instrument requires it, that is, when the MICADO OCM signals the start of a scientific exposure.

To interpret and execute high-level commands, a local sequencer is employed. This sequencer is launched by the **Client Instrument Minion (CIM)**, which serves as the single point of access for the external client instrument. Section 3 explores in detail the role of the CIM in the communication between MORFEO and MICADO.

2.2 SAPO: Software for AIT Phase Operations

A new software tool, named **SAPO** (Software for AIT Phase Operations), will be developed to support MORFEO integration and testing activities. In general, the AIT devices are located in different parts of the MICADO Emulator System (MES) and in the Post Focal Relay (PFR), and can be grouped into: the Test and Alignment Camera (TAC); a scaled version of the TAC (mini-TAC); a scaled version of the Calibration Unit.

SAPO will interface with MORFEO ICSS at the template level, providing a simplified environment for test execution and monitoring during the Assembly, Integration, and Testing (AIT) phase. The SAPO architecture will consist of one FCS, nine DCSs, all based on the IFW CCF, and one Supervisor. In total, it will control thirteen devices. The decision to group the AIT functionalities into a dedicated software tool, rather than integrating them directly into the MORFEO ICSS, offers several advantages:

- increases modularity;
- reduces system complexity during the testing phase;
- allows independent development and debugging of AIT-specific procedures without affecting the main control software.

From a practical perspective, SAPO will interface MORFEO ICSS in a straightforward manner. Complete visibility and access to SAPO tasks will be provided at the consul level, allowing the MORFEO Sequencer to directly access and control the SAPO FCS when required.

3. MICADO AND MORFEO SOFTWARE INTERFACE ARCHITECTURE

The communication interface between the MICADO and MORFEO instrument control software is managed through a dedicated software architecture based on a CII-MAL server called Client Instrument Minion. CIM, developed using ESO's Rapid Application Development (RAD) toolkit [3], acts as a gateway between MICADO and MORFEO Local Sequencer. It receives commands defined in the MORFEO_TPL_LIB library and issued by MICADO. On the MORFEO side, the CIM loads a corresponding template into the MORFEO Local Sequencer and runs it.

3.1 Design and Architectural Advantages

The CIM's design is based on a modular architecture that offers significant operational and maintenance benefits:

- **Decoupling of Complexity:** CIM isolates the complexity of MORFEO specific commands from the MICADO interface, exposing a simplified and well-defined set of commands.
- **Interface Simplicity:** The architecture features three main interfaces:
 - `stdif` for managing the component's lifecycle commands;
 - `morRecif` for MORFEO to control CIM's state;
 - `morif`, the only interface used by MICADO, which implements the commands defined in the ICD[1].
- **State Control:** The `morRecif` interface allows the MORFEO to change CIM's state (e.g., enabling or disabling MICADO access), providing granular control over operations.
- **Maintenance and Flexibility:** Complex command logic is encapsulated in templates, making CIM easy to maintain. Operators can monitor the execution of templates via the MORFEO sequencer GUI, retaining full control over the execution of any step, stopping it or aborting it.

3.2 State Machine and Commands

Figure 1. CIM State Machine

The behavior of CIM is governed by a standard state machine provided by the RAD toolkit with minimal modifications as shown in Figure 1. Transitions between states are triggered by commands, which fall into three categories:

- Standard commands (`stdif`): manage the general state of the component (e.g., `init`, `enable`, `disable`).
- Control commands (`morRecif`): enable transitions between operational states (e.g., `recMicOn`, `abort`).
- Interface commands (`morif`): implement ICD-defined commands for specific operations (e.g., `register`, `configure`).

3.3 Advantages of the Selected Architecture

Adopting the RAD architecture for the CIM's implementation offers several advantages over a traditional Python library solution with integrated business logic:

- **Reduced Dependencies:** The design minimizes external dependencies on the MICADO side. The complex logic of the `MORFEO_TPL_LIB` commands is completely encapsulated within templates. The only requirements for MICADO are a simple Python library for creating interface objects and the XML file that defines the ICD (Interface Control Document). This approach ensures that MICADO's codebase is not burdened with MORFEO's internal command logic.
- **Flexibility and Versioning:** The interface is integrated into the MORFEO and MICADO projects using `git submodule add`. This provides a very simple and flexible way to manage versioning: the submodule code is only updated when actively triggered, meaning it does not automatically pull changes. It is also easy to switch to a different branch or version of the submodules (e.g. to test a bug-fix or a new feature).
- **Single Point of Access:** The architecture provides a single point of access for MICADO, simplifying access management and control of operations for MORFEO.
- **Simplified Maintenance:** Maintenance is significantly streamlined as updates to the command logic only require modifying the Python template files in MORFEO control software. There is no need to restart or redeploy the CIM server itself, allowing for a more agile development cycle and reducing potential downtime.

4. CONTROL AND MONITORING OF DEFORMABLE MIRRORS (DMS)

The Morfeo deformable mirrors are supplied by Adoptica, inclusive of dedicated control electronics and a workstation. The DMs can be operated either in real-time via a deterministic network or manually through the dedicated workstation. By design, this workstation interfaces with the system using the CII-MAL framework, supporting the commands detailed in Table 1.

To manage this interface, the ICSS implements a specialized device class. While fully integrated into the standard Function Control Framework, this component utilizes CII-MAL for communication instead of the conventional OPC UA protocol. Figure 2 illustrates the class diagram for this special device. The `pdmshape` component includes a dedicated widget, synchronized via CII calls to the DM workstation, and a custom panel that displays the real-time mirror shape and provides access to all functionalities defined in the DM interface.

Method	Return Value	Parameters	Description
<code>getShape</code>	array	none	Get Current Shape
<code>setShape</code>	integer	array	Set Shape
<code>setState</code>	integer	integer	Request State change in the SM
<code>setDeltaShape</code>	integer	array	To add a differential shape to the current one
<code>getSubState</code>	integer	none	Get current substate
<code>getError</code>	integer	none	To get last error information
<code>setRealTimeControl</code>	integer	bool	To switch the control of the DM between RTC and ICSS
<code>getRealTimeControl</code>	integer	none	To get current control flag

Table 1. Interface between DM workstation and ICSS

Figure 2. Special Device pdmshape class diagram

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The MORFEO ICSS has reached a mature and coherent architectural definition, aligned with the ELT software standards and designed to ensure modularity, robustness, and maintainability. The clear separation between MCAO and SCAO functionalities allows independent development and testing while maintaining a consistent supervisory and coordination layer.

The implementation of the Client Instrument Minion represents an effective solution for managing the interaction between MORFEO and MICADO. Its RAD-based design provides a clean abstraction layer that encapsulates the adaptive optics logic within MORFEO, while offering MICADO a transparent and simplified interface. This architecture minimizes interdependencies, eases maintenance, and supports flexible versioning strategies.

The integration of the Post-Focal Deformable Mirrors within the ICSS based on CII-MAL, ensures reliable control of the mirrors and compatibility with ESO control frameworks. The approach guarantees both real-time operability and manual command capabilities for testing and calibration activities.

Future work will focus on the validation of the SAPO framework for AIT operations, the integration and end-to-end testing with MES, and the improvement of PFDMs control and monitoring tools as well as the refinement of CIM. These developments will consolidate the readiness of MORFEO for the Final Design Review.

The MORFEO ICSS design represents a significant step toward operational maturity, providing a flexible and robust software foundation that will support the delivery of diffraction-limited performance for MICADO at first light on the ELT.

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